

Journal of Safety Research

Safety in High-Reliability Organizations: The Role of Upward Voice, Team Learning, and Safety Climate --Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	
Article Type:	Full Length Article
Keywords:	Upward voice, Safety performance, Team learning, Safety climate, High reliability organizations
Corresponding Author:	Inmaculada Silla University of Valencia Research Institute of Personnel Psychology, Organizational Development and Quality of Working Life SPAIN
First Author:	Ma. Julie-Anne Gajudo
Order of Authors:	Ma. Julie-Anne Gajudo Inmaculada Silla Francisco J. Gracia
Manuscript Region of Origin:	Europe
Abstract:	Maintaining and sustaining safety is extremely critical in high-reliability organizations. Upward voice contributes to a proactive approach to safety and allows the early identification of potential problems before they cascade into tragic consequences. Despite its relevance, research tends to focus on the antecedents of upward voice rather than its consequences or the mechanisms and boundary conditions that explain its potential benefits for safety. This study responds to this research gap by examining the relationship between upward voice and safety performance (safety compliance and participation), and the mediating role of team learning in this relationship. The current study also explores the moderating effect of safety climate on both the direct and indirect effect of upward voice on safety performance. The sample was composed of 617 workers from two nuclear power plants of the same organization. Results revealed a moderated mediation effect: the indirect effect of upward voice on safety performance through team learning was conditional upon the level of safety climate. As safety climate increases, the indirect positive effect becomes stronger.
Suggested Reviewers:	Anna-Maria Teperi anna-maria.teperi@ttl.fi Anna-Maria Teperi is Chief researcher at the "Occupational Safety, Finnish Institute of Occupational Health". She has extensive experience as a researcher and practitioner in a wide range of safety-critical organizations and other work environments. The focus of her work is the research and development of safety management and safety culture in high-reliability organizations. Kristina Potočnik kristina.potocnik@ed.ac.uk Kristina Potočnik is Professor and Chair of Organisational Behaviour at The University of Edinburgh. Among her research interests are safety, leadership, and high-performing and resilient teams. Moreover, she is Associate Editor of the Journal of Management Studies journal.

Dear Editor,

Please, find enclosed our manuscript “Safety in High-Reliability Organizations: The Role of Upward Voice, Team Learning, and Safety Climate”, which we would like to submit to Journal of Safety Research.

Best regards,

Highlights

- High reliability organizations need a proactive approach to safety.
- Upward voice and safety behaviors contribute to a proactive approach to safety.
- Upward voice is positively associated with safety compliance and participation.
- Team learning mediates the relationship between upward voice and safety behaviors.
- The indirect effect of team learning is greater when safety climate is high.

TITLE PAGE

Title: Safety in High-Reliability Organizations: The Role of Upward Voice, Team Learning, and Safety Climate

Authors:

Ma. Julie-Anne Gajudo[#]

University of Valencia

Blasco Ibáñez, 21, 46010 Valencia, Spain

mja.gajudo@gmail.com

Inmaculada Silla^{*#}

Corresponding author

IDOCAL. University of Valencia

Blasco Ibáñez, 21, 46010 Valencia, Spain

inmaculada.silla@uv.es

Francisco J. Gracia

IDOCAL. University of Valencia

Blasco Ibáñez, 21, 46010 Valencia, Spain

francisco.gracia@uv.es

[#]These authors contributed equally to this work

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

**Safety in High-Reliability Organizations:
The Role of Upward Voice, Team Learning, and Safety Climate**

1
2
3
4 **Abstract**
5

6 Maintaining and sustaining safety is extremely critical in high-reliability organizations. Upward
7 voice contributes to a proactive approach to safety and allows the early identification of potential
8 problems before they cascade into tragic consequences. Despite its relevance, research tends to
9 focus on the antecedents of upward voice rather than its consequences or the mechanisms and
10 boundary conditions that explain its potential benefits for safety. This study responds to this
11 research gap by examining the relationship between upward voice and safety performance (safety
12 compliance and participation), and the mediating role of team learning in this relationship. The
13 current study also explores the moderating effect of safety climate on both the direct and indirect
14 effect of upward voice on safety performance. The sample was composed of 617 workers from
15 two nuclear power plants of the same organization. Results revealed a moderated mediation effect:
16 the indirect effect of upward voice on safety performance through team learning was conditional
17 upon the level of safety climate. As safety climate increases, the indirect positive effect becomes
18 stronger.
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40

41 **Keywords:** Upward voice, Safety performance, Team learning, Safety climate
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 **1. Introduction**
5

6 High-reliability organizations (HROs), such as nuclear power plants, petrochemical
7 plants, or aviation are complex systems in which safety is a critical component when it comes to
8 achieving success and preventing catastrophic accidents. In this regard, upward voice becomes
9 crucial. It is necessary for employees to feel free to communicate their concerns, or any
10 challenging information, to their superiors. In this way, when a supportive environment is
11 cultivated, upward voice can help maintain safety in the long term (Bashshur & Oc, 2015).
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20

21 This study examines the influence of upward voice on safety performance, the underlying
22 mechanism explaining this relationship, and how the context in which voice occurs may
23 influence this process. In this way, we contribute to previous research based on a systemic
24 proactive approach to safety. In HROs, characterized by complexity and high interdependence
25 (Perrow, 1984), catastrophic failures “*are often preceded by smaller failures that were not*
26 *identified as being worthy of examination and learning*” (Cannon & Edmonson, 2005). Thus,
27 HROs must constantly work on anticipating these potential problems through proactive and
28 timely detection of errors and failures (Dekker & Pruchniki, 2013; Oliver et al., 2017a). Upward
29 voice can enable such early identification of potential problems and areas for improvement that
30 will stimulate team learning and, in turn, safety performance (Teperi et al., 2017). Moreover,
31 safety climate can play a relevant role in this process (DeJoy, 1996), acknowledging the
32 relevance of contextual factors and the need to adopt a systemic approach to safety.
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49

50 In addition, this study recognizes employees’ positive contributions to safety. First, it
51 focuses on upward voice, which assumes employees can play a valuable and active role in their
52 workplace. Second, it attempts to predict safety performance operationalized as safety behaviors
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 rather than individual errors. This approach is also congruent with a proactive approach aimed at
5
6 safety behaviors rather than accidents.
7
8

9 Previous research on upward voice has mainly focused on its antecedents (e.g.,
10 leadership) (Curcuruto & Griffin, 2023; Liu et al., 2023; Nazir et al., 2021; Silla et al., 2020a)
11 rather than its outcomes (e.g., Mohammad et al., 2023). There are only two studies that we are
12 aware of (Chen & Chen, 2014; Newnam et al., 2021), which have focused on different forms of
13 voice and safety. However, the relationship between upward voice and safety performance
14 remains unexplored, as well as the mechanisms and boundary conditions underlying these
15 relationships. This study addresses this research gap.
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24

25
26 Therefore, the current study explores the relationship between upward voice and safety
27 performance, and the mediating role of team learning in this relationship (Figure 1). It also
28 considers the moderating effect of safety climate on the relationship between voice and learning.
29 Safety climate is expected to moderate the indirect effect of upward voice on safety performance.
30
31 Finally, in line with a proactive approach to safety, this model aims to predict safety performance
32 by considering both safety compliance and participation.
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42

43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59 **Figure 1. Conceptual Model**
60
61

2. Theoretical background

2.1. Safety Performance: Compliance and Participation

In this study, safety performance is defined as a set of individual behaviors that contribute to safety achievement in organizations (Martinez-Corcoles, et al., 2018). It follows the safety performance model developed by Griffin and Neal (2000), which distinguishes between safety compliance and safety participation. This approach responds to the need to move from a reactive to a proactive approach to safety (Haage, 2021), which recognizes employees' active role and their contribution to safety (Hollnagel, 2018; Teperi, 2021; Teperi et al., 2023). Lessons learned in the field of safety in nuclear power plants (e.g., accidents such as Three Mile Island 1979, Chernobyl 1986, and Fukushima 2011) support this approach (Haage, 2021).

By reframing our understanding of safety to focus on behaviors that promote it, we can implement a forward-looking approach. Safety behaviors act as safety leading indicators. They have predictive value (Zwetsloot et al., 2020) and are actionable in that they can help reduce risk (Sinelnikov et al., 2013). Monitoring safety behaviors enables the organization to be proactive and to improve its safety before potential degradation cascades into an accident. By contrast, safety outcomes (e.g., number of accidents or injuries), which are lagging indicators, do not provide guidelines for improvement (Zwetsloot et al., 2020) and lack predictive value. Thus, considering that accidents in HROs can be life-threatening (Sutcliffe, 2011), measuring safety performance through leading indicators such as safety compliance and participation is worthwhile.

Safety compliance reflects activities that are key to safety and must be carried out by employees to guarantee the safety levels required by the organization and the different regulatory

1
2
3
4 bodies (Martinez-Corcoles, et al., 2018). Safety compliance is the basis and foundation for
5
6 achieving good safety outcomes (INSAG-15, 2002).
7
8

9 Safety participation refers to voluntary engagement in safety-related activities (e.g.,
10 participation in safety meetings, safety discussions with colleagues...) and complements safety
11 compliance (Martinez-Corcoles, et al., 2018). For instance, safety participation will contribute to
12 safety when unanticipated circumstances occur and standardized safety procedures on how to act
13 do not exist (Martínez-Corcoles et al., 2012; Zohar, 2008). Indeed, safety participation may
14 prevent safety routinization, which neglects potential unanticipated circumstances that have not
15 been considered in the system design stages (Casey et al., 2017; Frischknecht, 2005; Oliver et al.,
16 2019). In addition, safety participation rests on proactive voluntary actions that evidence
17 employee's active role and their potential positive contributions to safety (Tušl et al., 2020). In
18 other words, safety participation recognizes individuals' valuable contributions rather than
19 focusing on errors or deviations from desired behaviors. In this sense, safety participation is
20 likely to increase chances for ongoing improvement rather than merely focusing on safeguarding
21 the status quo (Teperi et al., 2022).
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39

40 *2.2. Upward Voice and Safety Performance*

41 Consistent with a proactive approach to safety, this study examines the relationship
42 between upward voice and safety performance. Upward voice is defined as an informal and
43 voluntary communication of work-related issues by an individual to people who may enact
44 change, such as a supervisor or another person in a higher organizational position (Morrison,
45 2014). Particularly, this study focuses on upward voice targeted to supervisors. In a qualitative
46 study, Detert et al. (2013) posit that when voice is addressed to supervisors, employees are
47 inclined to self-censor low value ideas, filter those that are not yet fully formed, or contrast their
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 opinions with others before speaking up. To sum up, employees are generally cautious about
5
6 raising inadequate or harmful ideas to higher-power others (Detert & Edmondson, 2011).
7

8
9 Subsequently, upward voice is likely to be insightful and nurture employees' ability to act safely
10
11 and is targeted to supervisors who hold the power to take action on potential issues.
12

13
14 Altogether, the focus on upward voice and safety performance operationalized as safety
15
16 behaviors can help prevent the incubation of a disaster (Pidgeon, 1997). In HROs, academics and
17
18 practitioners claim that it is important for employees to openly share information, facts, thoughts,
19
20 and inputs related to safety regardless of status or level (Haage, 2021; International Atomic
21
22 Energy Agency, 2006). In complex tightly coupled systems, upward voice helps employees to
23
24 spot problems before they become bigger, make sense of emergent and unanticipated hazards,
25
26 inform a timely response, improve task processes, or prevent progressive system safety
27
28 degradation (Detert et al., 2013; Engemann & Scott, 2020).
29
30
31

32
33 Despite these arguments suggesting that upward voice might promote safety performance
34
35 in HROs, empirical evidence on this relationship is scarce. Morrison's (2014) narrative review
36
37 concludes that, overall, upward voice leads to desirable outcomes at the individual (e.g., Imran et
38
39 al., 2021), group (e.g., Detert et al., 2013), and organizational levels. However, research on the
40
41 influence of upward voice on safety performance is limited (e.g., Chen & Chen, 2014). Indeed,
42
43 several literature reviews (Bashshur & Oc, 2015; Morrison, 2014) on voice neglect its influence
44
45 on safety performance in their synthesis and integration of previous research.
46
47
48

49
50 Newnam et al. (2021) addressed the influence of safety voice on organizational safety
51
52 outcomes in a sample of employees working on high-speed roads. However, they do not address
53
54 voice targeted to supervisors and consider safety outcomes rather than behaviors. They found
55
56 that safety voice was negatively associated with self-reported near misses and secondary
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 incidents on the high-speed roads employees attend. However, Detert et al. (2013) claim the need
5
6
7 to consider the target of voice to better understand its effects rather than to examine the
8
9 correlates of an undifferentiated amount of voice.

10
11
12 Moreover, Chen and Chen (2014) have addressed the relationship between upward safety
13
14 voice and safety performance. Findings showed upward safety communication was positively
15
16 related to safety compliance and participation using a sample of cabin crew members working
17
18 for international airlines in Taiwan. Thus, research on the relationship between upward voice and
19
20 safety performance is scarce, apart from Chen and Chen (2014). However, these authors have
21
22 focused on upward voice related to safety issues. This study extends previous research by
23
24 examining the relationship between upward voice and safety performance in a different
25
26 organizational context, nuclear power plants. Our focus on upward voice rather than upward
27
28 safety voice is consistent with our proactive approach to safety, which recognizes the need to
29
30 point out small discrepancies to be able to address failures in the early stages (Weick & Sutcliffe,
31
32 2007). In complex tightly coupled systems, it is difficult to distinguish between safety and non-
33
34 safety related issues (Silla et al., 2017). Issues that appear to not be related to safety could signal
35
36 safety degradation (e.g., the event that occurred in Davis-Besse nuclear power plant in 2002).
37
38
39
40
41
42

43 To sum up, theoretical arguments and empirical evidence suggest that upward voice may
44
45 positively influence safety performance. However, to our knowledge, this relationship has not
46
47 been previously examined. Hypothesis 1 reads as follows:
48
49
50
51
52

53 *Hypothesis 1. Upward voice is positively related to safety performance (safety compliance and*
54
55 *safety participation).*
56

57 58 *2.3. The Mediating Role of Team Learning* 59 60 61 62 63 64 65

1
2
3
4 Continuous improvement and learning are important elements in HROs, such as nuclear
5 power plants (Koistinen, 2021). Organizational learning refers to the ability of an organization to
6 improve the attainment and development of competencies through a set of behaviors and
7 activities that enable better functioning over time (Breso et al., 2008).
8
9

10
11
12
13
14 This study addresses team learning. According to Huber (1991), teams hold a certain set
15 of behaviors and activities that facilitate the process of learning and can be grouped into four
16 dimensions (Bresó et al., 2008). First, *Continuous Improvement Seeking*, which highlights a
17 team's willingness to learn from past experiences and execute actions to improve. Second,
18 *Dialogue Promotion and Open Communication*, which emphasizes the open and honest
19 communication between the team regardless of the roles each of the members play. Third,
20 *Collaborative Learning*, which denotes the value placed on each team member as a source of
21 knowledge and resources for the whole team. Finally, *Strategic and Proactive Leadership*
22 *Promoting Team Development*, which anchors on the importance of the role the leader plays in
23 promoting these behaviors and the proactive development of members.
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37

38 High levels of upward voice are expected to facilitate team learning for several reasons.
39 First, an increased flow of information and awareness about employees' concerns when it comes
40 to organizational functioning will stimulate continuous team learning. Upward voice sets the
41 foundation for open communication and collaboration within the team. On the contrary, low
42 levels of upward voice might undermine learning. For instance, employees might be hiding
43 information that confronts organizational policies and objectives to prevent interpersonal risks
44 (e.g., creating unfavorable impressions, being judged as incompetent, or feeling embarrassed)
45 (Argyris, 1977). This would undermine team learning.
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 Second, upward voice is critical to truly learn from incidents and disturbances. In HROs,
5
6 where incidents are caused by different factors that might interact in different ways, upward
7
8 voice will nurture a deeper understanding of those contributing factors and their interrelationship
9
10 (Haunschild & Sullivan, 2002). Moreover, upward voice might encourage employees to adopt
11
12 learning behaviors such as discussing problems, asking for help, or admitting errors
13
14 (Edmondson, 1999).

15
16
17 Third, overall, upward voice prevents organizational inertia which diminishes team
18
19 learning. Sometimes it is necessary to question taken-for granted assumptions and routines
20
21 (Carroll, 1998; Pentland et al., 2022; Schöbel & Wahlström, in press). When upward voice is
22
23 high, employees have the chance to express their views and approach a problem from different
24
25 perspectives and sources of knowledge. Upward voice will help to learn new adaptative
26
27 behaviors and unlearn inefficient ones by exposing individuals to new paradigms and viewpoints
28
29 (Van der Vegt & Bunderson, 2005). Seemingly, upward voice is a prerequisite to prevent
30
31 “*groupthink*”, that is, the uniformity that emerges when members involved in a cohesive ingroup
32
33 reinforce one another’s tendency to perceive problems in similar ways (Janis, 1972). The need
34
35 for consensus would undermine critical thinking and the appraisal of alternative courses of action
36
37 (Jones, 2013).

38
39 Finally, upward voice can also make supervisors aware of any migration of the system
40
41 toward safety boundaries (Rasmussen, 1997), which is critical in HROs. Inputs and contributions
42
43 from different levels and sources within the organization provide critical information (Basten &
44
45 Haamann, 2018) about the situation in which the organization operates. Thus, it can help
46
47 supervisors to spot problems earlier and take appropriate actions to facilitate team learning and
48
49 problem solving (Detert et al., 2013).
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 Despite several theoretical arguments suggesting that upward voice would benefit team
5
6 learning, this relationship remains unexplored. However, some studies have shown the benefits
7
8 of upward voice in very specific contexts. For instance, Edmondson (2003) found that upward
9
10 voice contributed to the successful implementation of new technology for cardiac surgery in
11
12 interdisciplinary teams. Upward voice proved to be useful for learning new tasks that present
13
14 technical and interpersonal challenges. Therefore, the following hypothesis was formulated:
15
16
17
18
19
20

21 *Hypothesis 2. Upward voice will be positively related to team learning.*
22
23
24
25

26 Team learning is critical for safety performance. Indeed, in HROs, safety performance is
27
28 grounded in continuous learning and improvement processes that allow adopting the necessary
29
30 proactive approach for early identification of hazards and implementation of solutions (Salas et
31
32 al., 2020). Several studies in the field of railway, aviation, and mining (Baum & Dahlin, 2007;
33
34 Haunschild & Sullivan, 2002; Madsen, 2009) have shown that organizational learning decreases
35
36 accident rates. Along these lines, international organizations such as World Association of
37
38 Nuclear Operators (WANO) or the Institute of Nuclear Power Operations (INPO) acknowledge
39
40 the relevance of learning in nuclear power plants (Koistinen, 2021).
41
42
43
44

45 This study focuses on the influence of team learning on safety performance. Safety
46
47 emerges from applying knowledge gained at different levels—individual, group, and
48
49 organization—across the whole organization’s operations (Basten & Haamann, 2018). In HROs,
50
51 where safety rests on interdependent systems, the opportunity for team learning is high and
52
53 significant. Moreover, teams are better prepared than individuals to adapt, be flexible, and
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 respond to safety challenges (Jones, 2013; Salas et al., 2020). Teams could be portrayed as
5
6 catalysts of safety emergence in HROs.
7

8
9 Several arguments support the positive influence of team learning on safety performance.
10
11 First, team learning facilitates the development of competencies (e.g., knowledge, skills, and
12
13 attitude) relevant to safety. These competencies provide employees with direction on how to
14
15 implement safety rules and contribute proactively to the overall safety of the organization. Along
16
17 these lines, a meta-analysis has shown that safety knowledge is positively associated with safety
18
19 performance (Christian et al., 2009). Second, team learning facilitates system wide
20
21 understanding which is needed to engage in the continuous improvement of system safety.
22
23 Complex systems are continuously adapting to design flaws and responding to practical drifts of
24
25 safety (Schöbel & Wahlström, in press) which requires employees to hold a system wide
26
27 perspective and engage in alternative ways to accomplish work safely.
28
29
30
31
32

33
34 Empirical evidence supports the positive relationship between team learning and safety
35
36 compliance (Ayenew et al., 2015) and participation (Martínez-Corcoles et al., 2012) in nuclear
37
38 power plants. To sum up, despite previous research on the relationship between team learning
39
40 and safety performance being scarce, theoretical and empirical evidence suggest that team
41
42 learning will enhance safety performance.
43
44

45
46 This study builds upon previous research by examining the mediating role of team
47
48 learning in the relationship between upward voice and safety performance. Upward voice is
49
50 expected to facilitate team learning by providing informational resources and new insights,
51
52 stimulating dialectical inquiry, or setting the basis for collaboration within the team. It is also
53
54 expected to prevent organizational inertia and *groupthink*, and raise awareness among
55
56 supervisors. In turn, team learning is expected to increase safety compliance and participation.
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 Upward voice, through team learning, will therefore cultivate a system-wide perspective and
5
6 establish directions for enhancing safety performance. It will make employees capable of
7
8 performing safely in different circumstances and engage in safety activities. Employees will be
9
10 able to manage complexities in the environment and adapt safely to organizational disturbances
11
12 (e.g., Bashshur & Oc, 2015).
13

14
15
16 Despite previous research suggesting the potential mediating role of team learning in the
17
18 relationship between upward voice and safety performance, we are not aware of any study
19
20 addressing this link. Thus, this study builds upon previous research by testing the following
21
22 hypothesis:
23

24
25
26 *Hypothesis 3. Team learning mediates the relationship between upward voice and safety*
27
28 *performance (safety compliance and safety participation).*
29

30 31 *2.4. The Climate of Safety* 32

33
34 This study also examines whether safety climate affects the influence of upward voice on
35
36 team learning. Organizational climate is defined as the employees' shared perceptions of the
37
38 policies, procedures, and practices that are rewarded, supported, and expected in the organization
39
40 (Schneider & Barbera, 2014). Following this definition, safety climate relates to the policies,
41
42 procedures, and practices related to safety (Zohar, 2008), which is one of the overriding priorities
43
44 in HROs. Based on symbolic social interactionism theory, safety climate arises because of
45
46 individuals' social interaction in seeking to comprehend their work environment (Zohar &
47
48 Hofmann, 2012). Over time, individuals' perceptions are expected to converge and contribute to
49
50 the emergence of a safety climate. The safety climate will then serve as a framework for the
51
52 interpretation of valued and adaptative behaviors (Neal & Griffin, 2004; Zohar, 2010). Thus, the
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 processes that upward voice triggers are conditional upon the frame of reference that safety
5
6 climate provides.
7

8
9 Therefore, in HROs, when exploring the context in which voice occurs, safety climate
10 will be critical. Several authors (Bashshur & Oc, 2015; Lockett et al., 2015; Nacioglu, 2016)
11 have claimed the need to explore the context in which voice takes place. In their exhaustive
12 review of the literature on voice, Bashshur and Oc (2015) suggest that considering organizational
13 climate is important to better understand the effects of upward voice. This study responds to this
14 research gap by exploring the role of safety climate.
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22

23 The study advocates that safety climate will cultivate a supportive upward voice
24 environment. Several arguments support this postulate. First, when safety climate is high, both
25 supervisors and coworkers are more likely to view upward voice as being valuable and welcome
26 and to respond favorably to it. Subsequently, upward voice is more likely to elicit team learning
27 under these favorable conditions. This might trigger a virtuous cycle on voice, as claimed by
28 some authors (Bashshur & Oc, 2015). Second, safety climate serves as an interpretative
29 framework guiding behaviors that will encourage the adoption of learning behaviors when
30 employees raise their concerns. The search for excellence and continuous improvement that
31 features high safety climate environments will strengthen the positive relationship between
32 upward voice and team learning.
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47

48 Despite the scarcity of empirical evidence delving into the context in which upward voice
49 occurs, some studies suggest that safety climate may affect the outcomes of upward voice. Chen
50 and Hou (2016) have shown that climate shapes how voice behavior translates into increased
51 individuals' creativity which is a critical element for learning. These authors found that the
52 positive relationship between voice behavior and creativity was stronger when the climate for
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 innovation was high. Thus, climate is a relevant boundary condition that modulates the effects of
5
6 voice behavior. In addition, we posit that in HROs, where safety is critical, safety climate will
7
8 become a relevant situational factor that can mitigate or intensify the effects of upward voice.
9
10 For instance, empirical evidence has proven that safety climate moderates the effects of
11
12 individual factors such as employee engagement. Mark et al. (2007) found that when the safety
13
14 climate is high, highly engaged nurses are less likely to suffer work injuries.
15
16
17
18

19 This study contributes to extending previous literature by shedding light on the context
20
21 that shapes the influence of upward voice on team learning and the boundary conditions that
22
23 influence the relationship between upward voice and team learning in HROs. Therefore, the
24
25 following hypothesis was formulated:
26
27
28
29
30

31 *Hypothesis 4. Safety climate moderates the relationship between upward voice and team*
32
33 *learning such that the relationship is stronger when the safety climate is high.*
34
35
36
37

38 To sum up, safety climate plays a relevant role in shedding light on the relationship
39
40 between upward voice and team learning. Moreover, if safety climate is expected to moderate the
41
42 relationship between upward voice and team learning, then it follows that the indirect effect of
43
44 upward voice on safety performance via team learning will be contingent on safety climate. This
45
46 study theorizes that the indirect positive effect of upward voice on safety performance through
47
48 team learning will be stronger when the safety climate is high.
49
50
51
52

53 *Hypothesis 5. Upward voice influences safety performance through its indirect effect via team*
54
55 *learning, and the indirect effect will be stronger when the safety climate is high.*
56
57

58 **3. Method**

59
60
61
62
63
64
65

3.1. Sample and Design

The sample consisted of 617 workers from two nuclear power plants from the same organization. All responsibility levels and functional areas in the nuclear facility were surveyed and the response rate was 76.55%. Most participants (73.2%) were older than 45 years, 21.3% were between 30 and 45 years of age, and 5.5% were less than 30 years old. Nearly half of the participants (54.3%) were university graduates. The study employed a cross-sectional research design with variables measured quantitatively using questionnaires.

3.2. Procedure

The study was conducted following international ethics guidelines developed by the American Psychological Association (APA). Questionnaires were distributed by the researchers through small group sessions in a quiet and convenient room during the employees' working time. At the beginning of each session, the researchers explained the purpose of the study and how the questionnaires should be completed. Participation was voluntary and anonymity and confidentiality were guaranteed. Participants were encouraged to answer honestly and take as much time as they needed to answer the questionnaire. They were also urged to ask questions and seek clarifications, if any, as researchers were available during the sessions to help and address any concerns.

3.3. Measures

Upward voice was measured with three items developed by the research team based on previous literature. They assess to what extent employees feel free to communicate their concerns or any challenging information to their superiors as an attempt to provide relevant insights (e.g., Silla et al., 2020b). The items read as follows: *"I can tell my supervisor when things are not going well"*, *"I can freely express any disagreements I have with my boss"*, and *"I*

1
2
3
4 *feel free to talk to my boss about any problems and difficulties I have in my job without any fear*
5 *at all*". The response scale ranged from 1 (*Completely disagree*) to 5 (*Completely agree*).

6
7
8
9 Team learning was assessed using the 20-item Team Learning Questionnaire by Bresó et
10 al. (2008). This scale has been validated and used in previous studies (Reneclé et al., 2020;
11 Martínez-Córcoles et al., 2012). It is based on a multidimensional model that measures four
12 dimensions: Continued Improvement Seeking, Dialogue Promotion and Open Communication,
13 Collaborative Learning, and Strategic and Proactive Leadership that Promote Learning. Some
14 sample items are: "*The lessons learned are made available to all the members*", "*Mistakes are*
15 *openly discussed in order to learn from them*", and "*Even when an error is stopped in time, it is*
16 *reported so that it does not happen again*". Response scale ranges from 1 (*Never or almost*
17 *never*) to 5 (*Always or almost always*).

18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31 Safety climate was measured using fifteen items adapted (Latorre et al., 2013) from the
32 Group Nuclear Safety Climate questionnaire (Zohar & Luria, 2005). This questionnaire has been
33 previously validated and used in other studies (de Castro, et al., 2017; Mezentseva et al., 2023;
34 Reneclé, et al., 2020). The questionnaire includes the following heading "*Below we present a*
35 *series of statements about NUCLEAR SAFETY. Please indicate to what extent you agree with*
36 *each of them with regard to your WORK UNIT*". Some sample items are "*There is a frequent*
37 *check on whether the safety norms and procedures are being followed*", "*We make sure we have*
38 *everything we need to do the job in a safe way*", "*The safety parameters are emphasized when*
39 *we are working under pressure*", and "*The inherent risks in our work are often referred to*". A
40 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 "*Strongly disagree*" to 5 "*Completely agree*" was used.

41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
66
67
68
69
70
71
72
73
74
75
76
77
78
79
80
81
82
83
84
85
86
87
88
89
90
91
92
93
94
95
96
97
98
99
100
101
102
103
104
105
106
107
108
109
110
111
112
113
114
115
116
117
118
119
120
121
122
123
124
125
126
127
128
129
130
131
132
133
134
135
136
137
138
139
140
141
142
143
144
145
146
147
148
149
150
151
152
153
154
155
156
157
158
159
160
161
162
163
164
165
166
167
168
169
170
171
172
173
174
175
176
177
178
179
180
181
182
183
184
185
186
187
188
189
190
191
192
193
194
195
196
197
198
199
200
201
202
203
204
205
206
207
208
209
210
211
212
213
214
215
216
217
218
219
220
221
222
223
224
225
226
227
228
229
230
231
232
233
234
235
236
237
238
239
240
241
242
243
244
245
246
247
248
249
250
251
252
253
254
255
256
257
258
259
260
261
262
263
264
265
266
267
268
269
270
271
272
273
274
275
276
277
278
279
280
281
282
283
284
285
286
287
288
289
290
291
292
293
294
295
296
297
298
299
300
301
302
303
304
305
306
307
308
309
310
311
312
313
314
315
316
317
318
319
320
321
322
323
324
325
326
327
328
329
330
331
332
333
334
335
336
337
338
339
340
341
342
343
344
345
346
347
348
349
350
351
352
353
354
355
356
357
358
359
360
361
362
363
364
365
366
367
368
369
370
371
372
373
374
375
376
377
378
379
380
381
382
383
384
385
386
387
388
389
390
391
392
393
394
395
396
397
398
399
400
401
402
403
404
405
406
407
408
409
410
411
412
413
414
415
416
417
418
419
420
421
422
423
424
425
426
427
428
429
430
431
432
433
434
435
436
437
438
439
440
441
442
443
444
445
446
447
448
449
450
451
452
453
454
455
456
457
458
459
460
461
462
463
464
465
466
467
468
469
470
471
472
473
474
475
476
477
478
479
480
481
482
483
484
485
486
487
488
489
490
491
492
493
494
495
496
497
498
499
500
501
502
503
504
505
506
507
508
509
510
511
512
513
514
515
516
517
518
519
520
521
522
523
524
525
526
527
528
529
530
531
532
533
534
535
536
537
538
539
540
541
542
543
544
545
546
547
548
549
550
551
552
553
554
555
556
557
558
559
560
561
562
563
564
565
566
567
568
569
570
571
572
573
574
575
576
577
578
579
580
581
582
583
584
585
586
587
588
589
590
591
592
593
594
595
596
597
598
599
600
601
602
603
604
605
606
607
608
609
610
611
612
613
614
615
616
617
618
619
620
621
622
623
624
625
626
627
628
629
630
631
632
633
634
635
636
637
638
639
640
641
642
643
644
645
646
647
648
649
650
651
652
653
654
655
656
657
658
659
660
661
662
663
664
665
666
667
668
669
670
671
672
673
674
675
676
677
678
679
680
681
682
683
684
685
686
687
688
689
690
691
692
693
694
695
696
697
698
699
700
701
702
703
704
705
706
707
708
709
710
711
712
713
714
715
716
717
718
719
720
721
722
723
724
725
726
727
728
729
730
731
732
733
734
735
736
737
738
739
740
741
742
743
744
745
746
747
748
749
750
751
752
753
754
755
756
757
758
759
760
761
762
763
764
765
766
767
768
769
770
771
772
773
774
775
776
777
778
779
780
781
782
783
784
785
786
787
788
789
790
791
792
793
794
795
796
797
798
799
800
801
802
803
804
805
806
807
808
809
810
811
812
813
814
815
816
817
818
819
820
821
822
823
824
825
826
827
828
829
830
831
832
833
834
835
836
837
838
839
840
841
842
843
844
845
846
847
848
849
850
851
852
853
854
855
856
857
858
859
860
861
862
863
864
865
866
867
868
869
870
871
872
873
874
875
876
877
878
879
880
881
882
883
884
885
886
887
888
889
890
891
892
893
894
895
896
897
898
899
900
901
902
903
904
905
906
907
908
909
910
911
912
913
914
915
916
917
918
919
920
921
922
923
924
925
926
927
928
929
930
931
932
933
934
935
936
937
938
939
940
941
942
943
944
945
946
947
948
949
950
951
952
953
954
955
956
957
958
959
960
961
962
963
964
965
966
967
968
969
970
971
972
973
974
975
976
977
978
979
980
981
982
983
984
985
986
987
988
989
990
991
992
993
994
995
996
997
998
999
1000

1
2
3
4 and Griffin (2006). The scale consists of three items, with a five- point Likert response scale
5
6 ranging from 1 (*Completely disagree*) to 5 (*Completely agree*). Scale items were: “*I use all the*
7
8 *necessary safety equipment to do my job*”, “*I use the correct safety procedures for performing*
9
10 *my job*”, and “*I ensure the highest levels of safety when I do my job*”.

11
12
13
14 Safety participation was assessed using the scale by Neal and Griffin (2006). The scale
15
16 consists of three items, with a 5-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (*Completely*
17
18 *disagree*) to 5 (*Completely agree*). Items read as follows: “*I promote the safety program within*
19
20 *the organization*”, “*I make extra effort to improve safety in the workplace*”, and “*I voluntarily*
21
22 *carry out tasks or activities that help to improve workplace safety*”. Previous studies using this
23
24 scale have displayed good validity and reliability results (Wang et al., 2022; Maneechaeye &
25
26 Portapiroon, 2022; Newnam et al., 2021).

30 31 *3.4. Analysis*

32
33 Descriptive and correlation analyses were carried out. Cronbach Alpha coefficients were
34
35 computed for all the scales using SPSS. Scale validity was examined through Confirmatory
36
37 Factor Analysis (CFA) using Jamovi.

38
39
40 Hypotheses were tested using several regression analyses. To test Hypothesis 1 and 2, a
41
42 simple regression analysis was used. To test Hypothesis 3, a mediation regression analysis was
43
44 conducted, specifically Model 4 (Hayes, 2013). To test Hypothesis 4, a moderation regression
45
46 analysis was carried out. Finally, for hypothesis 5, a first stage moderated mediation analysis was
47
48 computed using Model 7 (Hayes, 2013). PROCESS macro for SPSS was used to conduct these
49
50 analyses.
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive Statistics and Correlations

Descriptive statistics, reliability, and correlations are provided in Table 1. Reliability coefficients, as reported on the diagonal inside the parenthesis, reveal strong internal consistency across all measures used in the study. The patterns of correlations were also consistent with the theoretical and empirical arguments provided earlier. Upward voice was positively related to team learning and safety performance. Furthermore, team learning was positively related to safety performance. Reliability of all the variables were satisfactory, showing values above 0.80.

Table 1. Means, standard deviations, reliability, and correlations among study variables.

Variable	Range	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1. Upward Voice	1–5	3.93	1.01	(0.94)				
2. Team Learning	1–5	3.68	0.74	0.70**	(0.96)			
3. Saf. Climate	1–5	4.04	0.76	0.60**	0.78**	(0.96)		
4. Saf. Compliance	1–5	4.62	0.56	0.35**	0.47**	0.59**	(0.88)	
5. Saf. Participation	1–5	4.25	0.73	0.34**	0.48**	0.55**	0.62**	(0.87)

Note: ** $p < 0.01$. Reliability (coefficient alpha) is given in parentheses.

4.2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

To identify whether the scales in the study measure the intended factors, CFA was conducted using Jamovi software. For this study, including five scales, a pooled CFA for all measurement models was conducted following previous research recommendations (Awang, 2015).

The measurement model consisting of upward voice, team learning, safety climate, safety compliance, and safety participation showed an acceptable fit to the data (SRMR=.05; RMSEA=.078; CFI=.84). SRMR and RMSEA values were satisfactory. Additionally, RMSEA with a 90% CI (.076, .080) was also acceptable. The CFI, while close, was below the

recommended index values. However, Heene et al. (2011) cautioned against generalizing the rule-of-thumb cut-off fit criteria which need not be too strictly applied.

4.3. Hypothesis Testing

Unexpectedly, the relationship between upward voice and safety performance was not statistically significant ($c' = 0.02$) when team learning was controlled for (Hypothesis 1). As hypothesized (Hypothesis 2), upward voice was positively associated with team learning ($a = 0.51$). Team learning was also found to be positively related to safety performance when controlling for upward voice ($b = 0.39$) (See Table 2). All these relationships were revealed to be statistically significant. The bias–corrected bootstrap confidence interval for the indirect effect ($ab = 0.20$) based on 5000 bootstrap samples was above zero (95% confidence interval = 0.16–0.24). Thus, the results supported Hypothesis 3, which postulated that team learning would mediate the relationship between team learning and safety performance. Given that Hypothesis 1 was not supported, but the mediation effect was confirmed through Hypothesis 2 and 3, the findings reveal a full mediating relationship between upward voice and safety performance via team learning.

Table 2. Regression results for the mediation model.

Predictor	Team Learning			Safety Performance		
	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>
Constant	1.69	0.09	<0.001	2.92	0.10	<0.001
Upward Voice	0.51	0.02	<0.001	0.02	0.03	0.51
Team Learning	-	-	-	0.39	0.04	<0.001
	$R^2 = 0.483$			$R^2 = 0.273$		
	$F(1,612) = 570.588, p < 0.001$			$F(2,611) = 114.842, p < 0.001$		

To test the moderation effect of safety climate (SC) on the pathway of upward voice and team learning (Hypothesis 4), a moderation regression analysis was computed. As hypothesized,

safety climate moderated the relationship between upward voice and team learning ($B = 0.04$, $t = 2.20$, $p < 0.05$) (See Table 3). The interaction factor of upward voice and safety climate positively influenced team learning. Furthermore, the increase in explained variance when the interaction term was introduced in the model was statistically significant (R -square-change = 0.003, $F(1,609) = 4.838$, $p < 0.05$). In particular, the conditional effect of upward voice on safety performance at low, and high levels of safety climate was positive and statistically significant. The conditional effect was found to be greater at high, rather than low, levels of safety climate. As such, all the confidence intervals were above zero and there were no statistical significance transition points within the observed range of the moderator found using the Johnson–Neyman method.

Table 3. *Regression results for the moderation model.*

Predictor	Team Learning			Safety Performance		
	β	SE	p	β	SE	p
Constant	3.66	0.02	<0.001	2.99	0.14	<0.001
Upward Voice (UV)	0.27	0.02	<0.001	0.02	0.03	0.511
Team Learning				0.39	0.04	<0.001
Safety Climate (SC)	0.57	0.28	<0.001			
UV x SC	0.04	0.02	0.028			
	$R^2 = 0.6913$			$R^2 = 0.274$		
	$F(3, 609) = 454.552, p < 0.001$			$F(2, 610) = 115.156, p < 0.001$		

The graphical plot of the interaction effects (see Figure 2) revealed that the relationship between upward voice and team learning was stronger when the safety climate was high rather than low, albeit both are statistically significant. Moreover, those who reported a high upward voice and high safety climate showed the highest levels of team learning. Thus, the findings supported Hypothesis 4.

Figure 2. Plot of interaction between upward voice and safety climate (SC) in predicting team learning.

Finally, Hypothesis 5, which postulated first-stage moderated mediation wherein the indirect effect of upward voice on safety performance through team learning is conditional on safety climate, was tested. Results indicated that the conditional indirect effect of upward voice on safety performance was consistently positive and became stronger as the safety climate increased. Table 4 shows confidence intervals (CIs) for bootstrap tests at three safety climate values: (1) one standard deviation (SD) below the mean, (2) mean, and (3) one SD above the mean. The CIs were considered statistically significant if the range between the low and high CIs did not include zero (Hayes, 2013). The data revealed that this indirect effect is significant at all levels of safety climate as the range between low and high CIs did not include zero, which provided support for Hypothesis 5. Moreover, the index of moderated mediation which tested the difference between conditional indirect effects was significantly different from zero with an estimate of 0.17 (boot SE = 0.01; 95% confidence interval = 0.01 to 0.04). Overall, this result

indicates that the conditional indirect effects projected at multiple levels of safety climate were significantly different from each other. Thus, Hypothesis 5 was supported, such that the indirect and positive effect of upward voice on safety performance through team learning was observed when levels of safety climate were low to high. It can also be noted that the conditional indirect effect became stronger as the safety climate increased.

Table 4. *Bootstrap results for the conditional indirect effects.*

Safety Climate	Effect	BootSE	Boot Lower Limit 95% Confidence Interval	Boot Upper Limit 95% Confidence Interval
-1SD (-0.754)	0.09	0.013	0.07	0.12
M (0)	0.11	0.014	0.08	0.14
+1SD (0.754)	0.12	0.018	0.09	0.16

5. Discussion

This study tested a model that attempts to predict safety performance in HROs based on a systemic proactive approach to safety. With this purpose, upward voice was considered a relevant antecedent (Engemann & Scott, 2020; IAEA, 2006) of safety performance which was operationalized as safety behaviors (safety compliance and participation) (Neal & Griffin, 2000). The proposed model examined why upward voice may influence safety performance and under which conditions. Safety climate was considered a relevant contextual factor. As expected, results showed that upward voice facilitates team learning, which in turn increases safety performance (Hypothesis 3). Findings support a full mediation model given that the relationship between upward voice and safety performance was non-significant when team learning was controlled for (Hypothesis 1). As hypothesized, the indirect effect of upward voice on safety performance through team learning was conditional on the level of safety climate (Hypothesis 5):

1
2
3
4 upward voice stimulates safety performance through team learning to a greater extent when
5
6 safety climate is high.
7

8
9 As expected, upward voice influenced team learning (Hypothesis 2) and safety climate
10 intensified this positive relationship (Hypothesis 4). Employees who reported high upward voice
11 and high safety climate displayed the highest levels of team learning. Our findings were
12
13 consistent with previous research that supports the benefits of upward voice for the team's
14
15 successful implementation of new technologies and team learning (Edmondson, 2003). It is also
16
17 consistent with previous studies showing a positive relationship between team learning and
18
19 safety performance (Ayenew et al., 2015; Martínez-Corcoles et al., 2012) when controlling for
20
21 upward voice.
22
23
24
25
26
27

28
29 Unexpectedly, the direct effect of upward voice on safety performance turned out to be
30 non-significant when team learning was controlled for. Thus, our study suggests that a more
31
32 holistic model of the effects of upward voice on safety performance is necessary. For instance,
33
34 team learning and safety climate play a relevant role in better understanding the benefits of
35
36 upward voice. Previous research on upward safety communication (Chen & Chen, 2014) might
37
38 also benefit from a more comprehensive approach.
39
40
41
42

43 *5.1. Theoretical Implications*

44

45
46 The current study evidences the benefits of upward voice and the mechanisms and
47
48 boundary conditions that explain them. Despite academics (Engemann & Scott, 2020) and
49
50 professionals (IAEA, 2020 -Safety Culture Model) in the field of safety having acknowledged
51
52 the relevance of upward voice in HROs, we are not aware of any study that addresses its
53
54 influence on safety performance, and the underlying mechanisms explaining this relationship.
55
56
57 IAEA's Safety Culture Model (2020) emphasizes problem identification and raising concerns,
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 which resembles upward voice, as important qualities of healthy nuclear organizations. This
5
6 guideline is grounded on the experience of experts from the nuclear industry but does not
7
8 provide empirical evidence that supports its postulates. Therefore, the present study establishes
9
10 the foundation for developing sound theoretical models on upward voice and safety, and enables
11
12 evidenced-based management.
13
14

15
16 Furthermore, this study supports the point made by some authors (Bashshur & Oc, 2015;
17
18 Detert et al., 2013; Morrison, 2011) that the relationship between upward voice and its postulated
19
20 outcomes cannot be oversimplified. This study delves into the conditions under which voice
21
22 occurs and how it influences its effects on safety performance. Previous research has recognized
23
24 the importance of safety climate (Casey et al., 2017) and team learning (Salas et al., 2020) for
25
26 safety performance. However, it does not address how safety climate contributes to building a
27
28 supportive environment and intensifies the positive effect of upward voice on team learning and
29
30 the indirect effect of upward voice on safety performance through team learning.
31
32

33
34 The current study builds on previous research, showing the mediating role of team
35
36 learning in the upward voice–safety performance connection. Subsequently, it contributes to
37
38 upward voice theory development by providing insight into the mechanisms that explain the
39
40 benefits of upward voice in HROs (Bashush & Oc, 2015). Additionally, our findings support the
41
42 important role of team learning in HROs as suggested by previous researchers (Koistinen, 2021;
43
44 Salas et al., 2020).
45
46
47

48
49 The present study also contributes to the development of safety climate theory by
50
51 demonstrating that safety climate is a relevant contextual factor that helps understand the
52
53 relationship between upward voice and safety performance. Moreover, findings from the current
54
55 study are consistent with previous research that shows that safety climate is a relevant situational
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 factor to be considered when predicting safety (Mark et al., 2007). Results are also congruent
5
6 with previous studies that have shown that other facets of climate (e.g., innovation climate)
7
8 influence the effects of voice on relevant organizational outcomes (Chen & Hou, 2016).
9

10
11 Moreover, the present study provides theoretical arguments that may explain the role of
12 safety climate in the postulated model. The symbolic social interactionism postulates help to
13
14 understand the influence of safety climate in the process triggered by upward voice. Safety
15
16 climate may serve as a framework for the interpretation of valued and adaptive behaviors (Neal
17
18 & Griffin, 2004; Zohar, 2010). A safety climate may encourage employees and supervisors to
19
20 respond positively to upward voice for the sake of safety. Moreover, when the safety climate is
21
22 high, the search for continuous improvement to assure safety may encourage employees to adopt
23
24 learning behaviors when upward voice takes place. Future studies should explore whether safety
25
26 climate acts as a frame of interpretation that mitigates or aggravates the influence of other
27
28 relevant predictors of safety performance.
29
30
31
32
33
34

35
36 In addition, the proposed model contributes to the advancement of research in the field of
37 safety in HROs. The model is based on a proactive approach that predicts leading indicators of
38
39 safety (e.g., safety behaviors). Thus, it extends previous research focused on lagging indicators
40
41 (Luo, 2020) that attempt to predict safety outcomes (e.g., accident or injury rates) based on past
42
43 experience (Baum & Dahlin, 2007; Madsen, 2009).
44
45
46
47

48 Finally, this model will be insightful for system safety approach developments (Weick &
49
50 Sutcliffe, 2007) which acknowledge that front-line employees' suggestions, ideas, worries, and
51
52 concerns are crucial to prevent safety degradation in HROs. This study encourages system safety
53
54 approach academics to incorporate upward voice literature into their theoretical developments.
55
56
57
58 Upward voice may help to avoid safety degradation in the early stages. This approach is
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 necessary to prevent systemic weaknesses that have caused tragic accidents in the past (e.g.,
5
6 Three Mile Island in 1970, the Chernobyl accident in 1986, and the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear
7
8 power plant incident in 2011) (Haage, 2021). Additionally, the proposed conceptual model
9
10 incorporates contextual factors that can contribute to maintaining safety in the long run (e.g.,
11
12 safety climate).
13
14

15 16 *5.2. Practical Implications* 17

18
19 This study has relevant practical implications on how to promote sustained safety
20
21 performance, suggesting that organizations should promote organizational policies and practices
22
23 that support safety climate and team learning. Results suggest that HROs should cultivate a
24
25 strong safety climate that allows upward voice to translate into favorable safety outcomes.
26
27 Promoting a safety climate will intensify the indirect positive effect of upward voice on safety
28
29 performance. Without considering the safety climate, efforts to foster voice and learning to
30
31 improve safety performance may be less effective. Future studies could also explore whether
32
33 other safety related initiatives would also accomplish their goals more effectively when the
34
35 safety climate is high.
36
37
38
39

40
41 Moreover, programs and initiatives centered on promoting upward voice should monitor
42
43 organizational members' reactions to upward voice and make sure that they stimulate team
44
45 learning. This study suggests that upward voice increases safety performance by stimulating
46
47 team learning. Given that this study adopts a pragmatic approach to team learning that focuses on
48
49 behaviors, several recommendations can be made to inform organizational programs and
50
51 initiatives that pursue encouraging upward voice. Those initiatives should provide means,
52
53 resources, and working conditions that enable upward voice to foster continuous improvement,
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 open and honest communication within the team, and collaborative learning. Additionally,
5
6 upward voice should inform leaders' actions to promote learning and team development.
7
8

9 Finally, the current study suggests that policies encouraging upward voice may stimulate
10 team learning under favorable conditions. These findings may have practical implications for
11 organizations in complex, fast-paced environments where team learning is essential for their
12 survival (Oliver et al., 2017b). In these unpredictable environments, team learning capability
13 provides a competitive advantage.
14
15
16
17
18
19
20

21 *5.3. Limitations and Future Research Direction*

22

23 The current study presents some limitations. It is a cross-sectional study so causal
24 relationships cannot be assumed. Despite several theoretical arguments supporting the positive
25 influence of upward voice on team learning, this relationship could turn out to be reciprocal.
26
27 Longitudinal studies that consider voice as a process may provide further insight into this
28 relationship. A key assumption in the literature that supports the influence of upward voice on
29 team learning is that the motive for voice is generally intended to help the organization perform
30 better (Morrison, 2011), especially when it comes to upward voice (Detert et al., 2013).
31
32 However, one may argue that this relationship could be reciprocal. When team learning is well-
33 established, the perceived efficacy of voice may encourage employees' tendency to speak up,
34 given that individuals will consider that their inputs and contributions will be taken into account.
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47

48 Moreover, this study uses self-report measures, which may lead to common method bias.
49
50 However, following Podsakoff et al. (2012), several procedural strategies were used to mitigate
51 common method bias. Participants were assured of anonymity which helped to avoid social
52 desirability, and different anchor labels were used to measure the different variables included in
53 the study.
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 Despite its limitations, the current study is worthwhile and insightful for future research.
5
6
7 It sheds light on the conditions under which upward voice improves safety performance and
8
9 encourages others to follow the same line of research. This study has focused on upward voice
10
11 targeted to supervisors, but when voice is targeted to other organizational members (e.g., leaders
12
13 outside their chain of command, coworkers...), distinct outcomes and prerequisite conditions
14
15 will feature the different sender-target combination of voice (Detert et al., 2013). Future research
16
17 should address this issue as well as the role of context.
18
19

20
21 This study has been conducted in a particular context, the nuclear industry, where safety
22
23 climate is salient for organizational members. Future studies conducted in different types of
24
25 high-reliability organizations (e.g., petrochemical plants, aviation), that also place safety as a
26
27 core element in its daily operations, would inform about the generalizability of our findings.
28
29 Safety climate would also be salient in organizations that seek reliability (Weick & Sutcliffe,
30
31 2007). Future studies may go further by testing the role of different facets of climate in the
32
33 upward voice performance link. One might argue that in other organizational settings with
34
35 different priorities, the climate facet needed to better understand the effects of upward voice
36
37 might be different. Studies following this research path would enrich theoretical developments
38
39 that emphasize the importance of context for a better understanding of voice correlates (Bashshur
40
41 & Oc, 2015).
42
43
44
45
46
47

48 Moreover, a multilevel approach would also be valuable to learn about the group-level
49
50 features that build a supportive environment conducive to safety performance. This study
51
52 suggests that safety climate and team learning are relevant contextual factors for understanding
53
54 the relationship between upward voice and safety performance. However, we have not addressed
55
56 these aspects at the group level.
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 Moreover, future studies should consider upward voice as a process rather than a “*one-*
5
6
7 *shot exchange*” (Bashshur & Oc, 2015). Longitudinal studies would provide information about
8
9 voice as a process that considers colleagues' and supervisors' reactions (e.g., whether voice is
10
11 ignored or acknowledged), how voice dynamics change as a function of those reactions, and
12
13 whether voice stimulates organizational change through learning in the short and long term
14
15 (Bashshur & Oc, 2015; Engemann & Scott, 2020; Silla et al., 2020). This approach to voice
16
17 would enrich theoretical developments by incorporating a feedback loop from outcomes to voice
18
19 (Engemann & Scott, 2020).
20
21
22

23 **6. Conclusion**

24
25
26 This study encourages future research to move towards a proactive approach to safety,
27
28 acknowledging the value of employees' contribution through upward voice. It extends previous
29
30 research by showing the mechanisms and boundary conditions that explain the relationship
31
32 between upward voice and safety compliance and participation. Results revealed that upward
33
34 voice enhances safety compliance and participation through team learning to a greater extent
35
36 when the safety climate is high.
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 **REFERENCES**
5

6 Argyris, C., 1977. Double loop learning in organizations. *Harvard. Bus. Rev.* 55 (5), 115–125.
7

8 Awang, Z., 2015. *SEM Made Simple*. MPWS Publisher.
9

10 Ayenew, A.A., Gracia, F.J., Toderi, S., 2015. Linking trust to safety performance in nuclear
11 power plants: the mediating role of team learning. *CLEAR International Journal of*
12 *Research in Management, Science and Technology* 5 (10), 1–14.
13
14
15
16
17

18 Bashshur, M.R., Oc, B., 2015. When Voice Matters: A Multilevel Review of the Impact of Voice
19 in Organizations. *J. Manage.* 41 (5), 1530–1554. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206314558302>
20
21
22

23 Basten, D., Haamann, T., 2018. Approaches for Organizational Learning: A Literature Review.
24 *SAGE Open* 8 (3), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244018794224>
25
26
27

28 Baum, J.A., Dahlin, K.B., 2007. Aspiration Performance and Railroads' Patterns of Learning
29 from Train Wrecks and Crashes. *Organ. Sci.* 18 (3), 368–385.
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49

50 Bresó, I., Gracia, F.J., Latore-Navarro, M.F., Peiro, J.M., 2008. Development and validation of
51 the Team Learning Questionnaire. *Comportamento Organizacional e Gestao* 14 (2), 145–
52 160.
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

66 Cannon, M.D., Edmondson, A.C., 2005. Failing to Learn and Learning to Fail (Intelligently):
67 How Great Organizations Put Failure to Work to Innovate and Improve. *Long. Range.*
68 *Plann.* 38 (3), 299–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2005.04.005>
69
70
71
72
73
74
75
76
77
78
79
80
81
82
83
84
85
86
87
88
89
90
91
92
93
94
95
96
97
98
99
100

101 Carroll, J.S., 1998. Organizational learning activities in high- hazard industries: the logics
102 underlying self- analysis. *J. Manage. Stud.* 35 (6), 699–717. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6486.00116>
103
104
105
106
107
108
109
110
111
112
113
114
115
116
117
118
119
120
121
122
123
124
125
126
127
128
129
130
131
132
133
134
135
136
137
138
139
140
141
142
143
144
145
146
147
148
149
150
151
152
153
154
155
156
157
158
159
160
161
162
163
164
165

- 1
2
3
4 Casey, T., Griffin, M.A., Flatau Harrison, H., Neal, A., 2017. Safety climate and culture:
5
6 Integrating psychological and systems perspectives. *J. Occup. Health. Psych.* 22 (3), 341–
7
8 353. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ocp0000072>
9
- 10
11 Curcuruto, M., Griffin, M.A., 2023. Upward safety communication in the workplace: How team
12
13 leaders stimulate employees’ voice through empowering and monitoring supervision.
14
15 *Safety. Sci.* 157, 105947. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2022.105947>
16
17
- 18
19 Chen, C., Chen, S., 2014. Investigating the effects of safety management system practice,
20
21 benevolent leadership and core self-evaluations on cabin crew safety behavior. *Asian*
22
23 *transport studies* 3 (2), 187–204. <https://doi.org/10.11175/eastsats.3.187>
24
25
- 26
27 Chen, A.S., Hou, Y., 2016. The effects of ethical leadership, voice behavior and climates for
28
29 innovation on creativity: A moderated mediation examination. *Leadership. Quart.* 27 (1),
30
31 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2015.10.007>
32
- 33
34 Christian, M.S., Bradley, J.C., Wallace, J.C., Burke, M.J., 2009. Workplace safety: a meta-
35
36 analysis of the roles of person and situation factors. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 94 (5), 1103–1127.
37
38 <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0016172>
39
- 40
41 de Castro, B.L., Gracia, F.J., Tomás, I., Peiró, J.M., 2017. The Safety Culture Enactment
42
43 Questionnaire (SCEQ): Theoretical model and empirical validation. *Accident. Anal.*
44
45 *Prev.* 103 (1), 44–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2017.03.018>
46
47
- 48
49 DeJoy, D.M., 1996. Theoretical models of health behavior and workplace self-protective
50
51 behavior. *J. Safety. Res.* 27 (2), 61–72. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4375\(96\)00007-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4375(96)00007-2)
52
- 53
54 Dekker, S., Pruchniki, S., 2013. Drifting into failure: theorising the dynamics of disaster
55
56 incubation. *Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science* 15 (6), 534–544.
57
58 <https://doi.org/10.1080/1463922X.2013.856495>
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4 Detert, J.R., Burrell, E.R., Harrison, D.A., Martin, S.R., 2013. Voice Flows to and around
5
6 Leaders: Understanding When Units Are Helped or Hurt by Employee Voice. *Admin.*
7
8 *Sci. Quart.* 58 (4), 624–668. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0001839213510151>
9
10
11 Detert, J.R., Edmondson, A.C., 2011. Implicit voice theories: Taken-for-granted rules of self-
12
13 censorship at work. *Acad. Manage. J.* 54 (3), 461–488.
14
15 <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2011.61967925>
16
17
18 Edmondson, A.C., 1999. Psychological safety and learning behavior in work teams. *Admin. Sci.*
19
20 *Quart.* 44 (2), 350–383. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2666999>
21
22
23 Edmondson, A.C., 2003. Speaking Up in the Operating Room: How Team Leaders Promote
24
25 Learning in Interdisciplinary Action Teams. *J. Manage. Stud.* 40 (6), 1419–1452.
26
27 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6486.00386>
28
29
30 Engemann, K. N., Scott, C. W., 2020. Voice in safety-oriented organizations: Examining the
31
32 intersection of hierarchical and mindful social contexts. *Hum. Resour. Manage. R.* 30 (1).
33
34 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2018.05.002>
35
36
37 Frischknecht, A., 2005. A changing world: Challenges to nuclear operators and regulators. In N.
38
39 Itoigawa, B. Wilpert, & B. Fahlbruch. (Eds.), *Emerging demands for the safety of nuclear*
40
41 *power operations* (pp.5–15). CRC Press.
42
43
44 Griffin, M.A., Neal, A., 2000. Perceptions of safety at work: A framework for linking safety
45
46 climate to safety performance, knowledge, and motivation. *J. Occup. Health. Psych.* 5,
47
48 347–358. <https://doi.org/10.1037//1076-8998.5.3.347>
49
50
51 Haage, M. V., 2021. The urgent need to learn from Fukushima nuclear power accident—from
52
53 reactive to proactive through a systemic approach to safety. In A.-M. Teperi, & N.
54
55 Gotcheva (Eds.), *Human Factors in the Nuclear Industry* (pp. 251–273). Woodhead
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65 Publishing.

- 1
2
3
4 Haunschild, P.R., Sullivan, B.N., 2002. Learning from Complexity: Effects of Prior Accidents
5 and Incidents on Airlines' Learning. *Admin. Sci. Quart.* 47 (4), 609–643.
6
7
8
9 <https://doi.org/10.2307/3094911>
10
11 Hayes, A. F., 2013. *Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis: A*
12 *regression-based approach*. Guilford Press.
13
14
15
16 Heene, M., Hilbert, S., Draxler, C., Ziegler, M., Bühner, M., 2011. Masking misfit in
17 confirmatory factor analysis by increasing unique variances: a cautionary note on the
18 usefulness of cutoff values of fit indices. *Psychol. Methods.* 16 (3), 319–336.
19
20
21
22
23 <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0024917>
24
25
26 Hollnagel, E., 2018. *Safety-I and safety-II: the past and future of safety management*. CRC press.
27
28
29 Huber, G.P., 1991. Organizational Learning: The Contributing Processes and the Literatures.
30
31 *Organ. Sci.* 2, 88–115. <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.2.1.88>
32
33
34 Imran, M.K., Fatima, T., Sarwar, A., Iqbal, S.M.J., 2023. Will I speak up or remain silent?
35 Workplace ostracism and employee performance based on self-control perspective. *J.*
36 *Soc. Psychol.* 163 (1), 107–125. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224545.2021.1967843>
37
38
39
40 International Nuclear Safety Advisory Group, 2002. *Key Practical Issues in Strengthening Safety*
41 *Culture*, INSAG Series No. 15, IAEA. [https://www-](https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1137_scr.pdf)
42 [pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1137_scr.pdf](https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1137_scr.pdf)
43
44
45
46
47 International Atomic Energy Agency, 2006. *Application of the management system for facilities*
48 *and activities*. Safety guide. IAEA Safety Standards Series No. GS-G-3.1
49
50
51
52 International Atomic Energy Agency, 2020. *A Harmonized Safety Culture Model*. IAEA
53 Working Document.
54
55
56
57 Janis, I.L., 1972. *Victims of Groupthink: A psychological study of foreign-policy decisions and*
58 *fiascoes*. Houghton-Mifflin.
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4 Jones, G.R., 2013. *Organizational theory, design, and change*. Pearson Education Limited.
5
6
7 Koistinen, P., 2021. Toward learning organization—practices in Nuclear Power Plants. In A.-M.
8
9 Teperi, & N. Gotcheva (Eds.), *Human Factors in the Nuclear Industry* (pp. 239–247).
10
11 Woodhead Publishing.
12
13
14 Latorre, M.F., Gracia, F.J., Tomas, I., Peiro, J.M., 2013. Validation of the group nuclear safety
15
16 climate questionnaire. *J. Safety. Res.* 46, 21–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2013.03.005>
17
18
19 Liu, X., Mao, J.Y., Chiang, J.T.J., Guo, L., Zhang, S., 2023. When and why does voice sustain or
20
21 stop? The roles of leader behaviours, power differential perception and psychological
22
23 safety. *Applied Psychology* 72 (3), 1209–1247. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apps.12432>
24
25
26 Lockett, J.J., Barkley, L., Stichler, J., Palomo, J., Kik, B., Walker, C., Donnelly, J., Willon, J.,
27
28 Sanborn, J., O’Byrne, N., 2015. Defining Peer-to-Peer Accountability From the Nurse’s
29
30 Perspective. *J. Nurs. Admin.* 45 (11), 557–562.
31
32
33
34 Luo, T., 2020. Safety climate: Current status of the research and future prospects. *Journal of*
35
36 *Safety Science and Resilience* 1 (2), 106–119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnlssr.2020.09.001>
37
38
39 Madsen, P.M., 2009. These Lives Will Not Be Lost in Vain: Organizational Learning from
40
41 Disaster in U.S. Coal Mining. *Organ. Sci.* 20 (5), 861–875.
42
43 <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.1080.0396>
44
45
46 Maneechaeye, P., Potipiroon, W., 2022. Safety Climate and Safety Behaviors among Thai Pilots:
47
48 The Mediated Moderated Structural Equation Modeling Technique. *ABAC Journal* 42
49
50 (2), 128–150.
51
52
53 Mark, B.A., Hughes, L.C., Belyea, M., Chang, Y., Hofmann, D., Jones, C.B., Bacon, C.T., 2007.
54
55 Does safety climate moderate the influence of staffing adequacy and work conditions on
56
57 nurse injuries? *J. Safety. Res.* 38 (4), 431–446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2007.04.004>
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4 Martínez-Córcoles, M., Gracia, F.J., Peiro, J.M., 2018. Human Safety Performance in High-
5 Reliability Organizations: The Case of the Nuclear Industry. *Papeles del Psicólogo* 39
6
7 (3), 183–190.
8
9
- 10
11 Martínez-Córcoles, M., Schöbel, M., Gracia, F.J., Tomás, I., Peiró, J.M., 2012. Linking
12
13 empowering leadership to safety participation in nuclear power plants: A structural
14
15 equation model. *J. Safety. Res.* 43 (3), 215–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2012.07.002>
16
17
18
- 19 Mezentseva, A., Gracia, F.J., Silla, I., Martínez-Córcoles, M., 2023. The role of empowering
20
21 leadership, safety culture and safety climate in the prediction of mindful organizing in an
22
23 air traffic management company. *Safety. Sci.* 168, 106321.
24
25
26 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2023.106321>
27
28
- 29 Mohammad, S.S., Nazir, N.A., Mufti, S., 2023. Employee Voice: A Systematic Literature
30
31 Review. *FIIB Business Review* 1–15, <https://doi.org/10.1177/23197145231153926>
32
33
- 34 Morrison, E.W., 2011. Employee Voice Behavior Integration and Directions for Future
35
36 Research. *Acad. Manag. Ann.* 5 (1), 373–412.
37
38 <https://doi.org/10.1080/19416520.2011.574506>
39
40
- 41 Morrison, E., 2014. Employee Voice and Silence. *Annu. Rev. Organ. Psych.* 1, 173–197.
42
43 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-031413-091328>
44
45
- 46 Nacioglu, A., 2016. As a critical behavior to improve quality and patient safety in health care:
47
48 speaking up! *Safety in Health* 2 (10), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40886-016-0021-x>
49
50
- 51 Nazir, S., Shafi, A., Asadullah, M.A., Qun, W., Khadim, S., 2021. Linking paternalistic
52
53 leadership to follower's innovative work behavior: the influence of leader–member
54
55 exchange and employee voice. *European Journal of Innovation Management* 24 (4),
56
57 1354–1378. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-01-2020-0005>
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4 Neal, A., Griffin, M.A., 2004. Safety climate and safety at work. In J., Barling, M.R., Frone
5
6 (Eds.), *The Psychology of Workplace Safety* (pp. 15–34). American Psychological
7
8 Association.
9
- 10
11 Neal, A., Griffin, M.A., 2006. A study of the lagged relationships among safety climate, safety
12
13 motivation, safety behavior, and accidents at the individual and group levels. *J. Appl.*
14
15
16 *Psychol.* 91 (4), 946–953. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.91.4.946>
17
18
- 19 Newnam, S., Stephens, A., Muir, C., Bruce, S., Austin, T., Mazzeo, T., 2021. Safety outcomes
20
21 for incident responders operating on high speed roads: An analysis of the relationship
22
23 with behaviour, motivation and role clarity. *PloS one* 16 (3), e0247095.
24
25
26 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0247095>
27
28
- 29 Oliver, N., Calvard, T., Potočnik, K., 2017a. Cognition, technology, and organizational limits:
30
31 Lessons from the Air France 447 disaster. *Organ. Sci.* 28 (4), 729–743.
32
33
34 <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.2017.1138> <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.2017.1138>
35
- 36 Oliver, N., Calvard, T., Potočnik, K., 2019. Safe limits, mindful organizing and loss of control in
37
38 commercial aviation. *Safety. Sci.* 120, 772–780.
39
40
41 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2019.08.018>
42
- 43 Oliver, N., Senturk, M., Calvard, T.S., Potocnik, K., Tomasella, M., 2017b. Collective
44
45 mindfulness, resilience and team performance. In *Academy of Management Proceedings*
46
47 (Vol. 2017, No. 1, p. 12905). Academy of Management.
48
49
- 50
51 Pentland, B. T., Yoo, Y., Recker, J., Kim, I., 2022. From lock-in to transformation: A path-
52
53 centric theory of emerging technology and organizing. *Organ. Sci.* 33 (1), 194–211,
54
55
56 <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.2021.1543>
57
- 58 Perrow, C., 1984. *Normal Accidents: Living with High-Risk Technologies*. Basic Books.
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4 Pidgeon, N., 1997. The limits to safety? Culture, politics, learning and man-made disasters. J.
5
6 Conting. Crisis. Man. 5 (1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-5973.00032>
7
8
9 Podsakoff, P.M., MacKenzie, S.B., Podsakoff, N.P., 2012. Sources of Method Bias in Social
10
11 Science Research and Recommendations on How to Control It. Annu. Rev. Psychol. 63,
12
13 539–569. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-120710-100452>
14
15
16 Rassmusen, J., 1997. Risk management in a Dynamic Society: A modelling Problem. Safety. Sci.
17
18 27 (2), 183–213. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-7535\(97\)00052-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-7535(97)00052-0)
19
20
21 Reneclé, M., Gracia, F.J., Tomas, I., Peiró, J.M., 2020. Developing Mindful Organizing in
22
23 Teams: A Participation Climate is not Enough, Teams Need to Feel Safe to Challenge
24
25 their Leaders. Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology 36 (3), 181–193.
26
27 <https://doi.org/10.5093/jwop2020a18>
28
29
30 Salas, E., Bisbey, T.M., Traylor, A.M., Rosen, M.A., 2020. Can teamwork promote safety in
31
32 organizations? Annu. Rev. Organ. Psych. 7, 283–313. [https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-012119-045411)
33
34 [orgpsych-012119-045411](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-012119-045411)
35
36
37
38 Schneider, B., Barbera, K.M., 2014. *The Oxford Handbook of Organizational Climate and*
39
40 *Culture*. Oxford University Press.
41
42
43 Schöbel, M., Wahlström, B., under review. A note on paths through minefields, organizational
44
45 factors and controlling system safety. Submitted to Safety. Sci.
46
47
48 Silla, I., Navajas, J., Koves, G.K., 2017. Organizational culture and a safety-conscious work
49
50 environment: The mediating role of employee communication satisfaction. J. Safety. Res.
51
52 61, 121–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2017.02.005>
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4 Silla, I., Gracia, F.J., Peiró, J.M., 2020a. La conducta de “Voz” en las organizaciones de alta
5
6 fiabilidad [Upward voice in High Reliability Organizations]. In E. M. Lira (Coord.),
7
8 *Bienestar social: Organizaciones Saludables* (103–116). Tirant Lo Blanch.
9
10
11 Silla, I., Gracia, F.J., Peiro, J.M., 2020b. Upward Voice: Participative Decision Making, Trust in
12
13 Leadership and Safety Climate Matter. *Sustainability* 12 (9).
14
15 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12093672>
16
17
18
19 Sinelnikov, S., Inouye, J., Kerper, S., 2015. Using leading indicators to measure occupational
20
21 health and safety performance. *Safety. Sci.* 72, 240–248.
22
23 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2014.09.010>
24
25
26 Sutcliffe K.M., 2011. High reliability organizations (HROs). *Best practice & research. Clinical*
27
28 *anaesthesiology* 25 (2), 133–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpa.2011.03.001>
29
30
31 Teperi, A.M., 2021. Applying human factors in the nuclear industry—people as a presence of
32
33 positive capacity for improving safety. In A-M. Teperi & N. Gotcheva (Eds.), *Human*
34
35 *Factors in the Nuclear Industry* (pp. 25–54). Woodhead Publishing Series in Energy.
36
37 <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102845-2.00002-8>
38
39
40
41 Teperi, A.M., Kuula, T., Ala-Laurinaho, A., Viitanen, K., Salonen, T., Asikainen, I., Puro, V.,
42
43 Wahlström, M., 2022. Participative development for improving nuclear safety: results
44
45 and implications of three methods in nuclear maintenance work. *Finnish Institute of*
46
47 *Occupational Health.* <https://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-261-992-1>
48
49
50
51 Teperi, A.M., Paajanen, T., Asikainen, I., Lantto, E., 2023. From must to mindset: outcomes of
52
53 human factor practices in aviation and railway companies. *Safety. Sci.* 158, 105968.
54
55 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2022.105968>
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4 Teperi, A.M., Puro, V., Ratilainen, H., 2017. Applying a new human factor tool in the nuclear
5 energy industry. *Safety. Sci.* 95, 125–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2017.02.013>
6
7
8
9 Tušl, M., Rainieri, G., Fraboni, F., De Angelis, M., Depolo, M., Pietrantonio, L., & Pingitore, A.,
10
11 2020. Helicopter pilots' tasks, subjective workload, and the role of external visual cues
12 during shipboard landing. *Journal of Cognitive Engineering and Decision Making*, 14 (3),
13
14 242–257.
15
16
17
18
19 Van Der Vegt, G. S., Bunderson, J. S., 2005. Learning and performance in multidisciplinary
20 teams: The importance of collective team identification. *Acad. Manage. J.* 48 (3), 532–
21
22 547.
23
24
25
26 Wang, D., Wang, L., Wei, S., 2022. Effects of Authoritarian Leadership on Employees' Safety
27 Behavior: A Moderated Mediation Model. *Frontiers in Public Health* 10. [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.846842)
28
29 [10.3389/fpubh.2022.846842](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.846842)
30
31
32
33
34 Weick, K.E., Sutcliffe, K.M., 2007. *Managing the unexpected. Resilient performance in the age*
35 *of uncertainty*. Jossey-Bass.
36
37
38
39 Zohar, D., 2008. Safety climate and beyond: A multi-level multi-climate framework. *Safety. Sci.*
40
41 46 (3), 376–387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2007.03.006>
42
43
44 Zohar, D., 2010. Thirty years of safety climate research: Reflections and future directions.
45
46 *Accident. Anal. Prev.* 42 (5), 1517–1522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2009.12.019>
47
48
49 Zohar, D., Hofmann, D.A., 2012. Organizational culture and climate. In W. S. Kozlowski (Ed.),
50
51 *Oxford Handbook of Organizational Psychology* (pp. 643–666). Oxford University Press.
52
53
54 Zohar, D., Luria, G., 2005. A multilevel model of safety climate: Cross-level relationships
55 between organization and group-level climates. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 90, 616–628.
56
57 <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.90.4.616>
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Zwetsloot, G., Leka, S., Kines, P., Jain, A., 2020. Vision zero: Developing proactive leading indicators for safety, health and wellbeing at work. *Safety. Sci.* 130, 104890.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2020.104890>

Author biography

Julie-Anne Gajudo holds a Master's degree on Work, Organizational, and Personnel Psychology (WOP-P) (Erasmus Mundus Master). She has collaborated with IDOCAL research institute, and her main research interests are safety climate and performance. Currently she is a people management professional and leader with over 10 years of experience in the human resources field with skills and knowledge in Rewards, Talent Acquisition and development, and Employee Engagement.

Inmaculada Silla is PhD in Work and Organizational Psychology (PhD Best Award 2008, University of Valencia) and senior researcher. Since 2018, she is member of the IDOCAL research institute and she has previously worked as senior researcher at CISOT (Sociotechnical Research Institute) (2005-2018). She has extensive experience in safety in high reliability organizations research, consultancy and advisory work. Her research interests are safety in high reliability organizations, organizational and safety culture, and safety performance. She has published several articles in high impact factor journals such as European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology, Safety Science or Journal of Safety Research.

Francisco J. Gracia (Degree in Psychology -1992- and Doctor in Social and Organizational Psychology -1998- by the Universitat de València), is Associate Professor of the Department of Social Psychology at the Universitat de València. His research activity is carried out within the framework of IDOCAL (<https://www.uv.es/idocal>), the Research Institute for Human Resources Psychology, Organizational Development and Quality of Working Life. His research interests are safety culture and safety performance, and organizational processes in high reliability organizations such as leadership. He has published his research in international journals such as Safety Science, Accident Analysis and Prevention, Risk Analysis, Journal of Safety Research, Sustainability, Applied Psychology: An International Review, Journal of Vocational Behavior, and European Journal of Management, among others.

He has carried out human resources consulting activities in management training and development, personnel selection, performance management, competencies management, teamwork, innovation, and safety culture, to mention only the most important topics, and for both public and private organizations.

Declaration of Competing Interest: The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.